

Empowerment Journey of Teachers: Narratives As the Forefront of Educational Advancements

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Abstract. This qualitative study explored the lived experiences of public elementary school teachers in Koronadal Central Elementary School, District 1, Koronadal City Division, focusing on their perspectives, challenges, and strategies concerning teacher empowerment. The use of narrative inquiry and in-depth interviews with purposively selected participants, the study applied thematic analysis to derive meaningful insights from their personal narratives. The analysis revealed complex challenges faced by teachers at the forefront of educational advancement, including limited resources, heavy workloads, and emotional pressures. Teachers developed adaptive coping mechanisms such as engaging in continuous professional development, building collaborative support networks, and practicing personal resilience. The study also uncovered critical educational insights emphasizing the importance of teacher leadership, autonomy, and innovation in enhancing instructional quality and student outcomes. Findings showed that empowered teachers, even in resource-constrained settings, remain committed to professional growth and contribute meaningfully to educational transformation. The study recommends the promotion of inclusive leadership, sustained professional support, and policy reforms to foster a culture of empowerment within the education system.

KEY WORDS

1. Teacher empowerment 2. lived experiences 3. coping strategies

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1. Introduction

Teacher empowerment faces a significant problem due to the inconsistency and lack of coherence in the execution of empowerment initiatives across schools. Despite efforts to promote teacher empowerment, initiatives often lack the necessary structure and follow-through to create lasting impact. Teachers oftentimes receive limited opportunities to actively engage in decision-making or have the resources to implement new approaches effectively that indirectly effect on their empowerment. This disjointed implementation leads to frustration among teachers and prevents them from fully realizing their potential to contribute to educational advancements. In Australia, Collie (2021) stated that empowering teachers is essential for enhancing educational outcomes; however, several challenges hinder this process. A major problem in the implementation of teacher empowerment is the overwhelming workload and inadequate recognition of teachers' responsibilities, which leads to burnout and a reduced capacity for professional growth. This results in diminished job satisfaction and a lack of en-

agement, ultimately hindering the effectiveness of empowerment initiatives. Another challenge for teacher empowerment as emphasized by Erdogan and Cavl (2019) in Turkey, that it is the insufficient opportunities for professional growth and development. Many teachers report limited access to training programs that are essential for staying abreast of educational advancements. This scarcity of professional development opportunities restricts teachers' ability to enhance their skills and adapt to evolving educational demands. Consequently, teachers may feel stagnant in their careers, leading to decreased motivation and engagement. The lack of a supportive work culture further exacerbates these issues, as teachers often work in isolation without collaborative opportunities to share best practices. Singh and Singla (2023) in Indonesia, highlighted that teacher empowerment is significantly hindered by current educational policies that prioritize standardized testing and accountability over teacher autonomy and creativity. This focus restricts teachers' ability to adapt their instruction to meet the diverse needs of learners. As a result, the curriculum becomes narrow, limiting teachers' ability to engage learners in meaningful educational experiences. The pressure to meet performance metrics further exacerbates stress and job dissatisfaction among educators, greatly affecting the advancement of education. While in the Philippines, particularly in Bansalan, Davao del Sur, Baloran and Hernan (2020) pointed-out that teacher empowerment faces critical challenges in its implementation due to the rapid integration of technology in education. Teachers often struggle to adapt to new digital tools and platforms, which undermines their effectiveness in the classroom. The insufficient training and resources for technological integration only intensify these difficulties. Disparities in access to technology among learners create inequities in learning opportunities, further hindering teacher empowerment and their ability to deliver quality education. In Laguna, Blanco, Buenvenida, Tan, Yazon and Lustina (2022) stated that a significant problem with teacher empowerment is insufficient communication and collaboration among school leaders and teachers. When administrators do not involve teachers in decision-making, it leads to disempowerment and disengagement. This disconnect not only undermines teacher morale but also prevents the creation of a collaborative school culture. The absence of open communication channels presents a major barrier to achieving true teacher empowerment. While in Island Garden City of Samal, Davao del Norte Division, Ecarma (2024) highlighted that improper and insufficient teacher empowerment has a profound effect on educators' well-being, with inadequate support systems exacerbating stress and burnout. The lack of attention to mental health and well-being leaves teachers vulnerable to exhaustion and high levels of job dissatisfaction. Without proper empowerment, teachers may feel undervalued and unsupported, which can lead to attrition. Ultimately, the absence of effective empowerment strategies directly threatens teacher retention and the overall effectiveness of the educational system. Locally, a study conducted in Koronadal City by Mangindalat (2022) emphasized that teacher empowerment has been inadequately implemented by school heads because of societal disregard of the teaching profession. Teachers often receive limited recognition for their contributions, which can affect their self-esteem and professional identity. This lack of appreciation can lead to decreased job satisfaction and higher turnover rates. Addressing this issue requires a cultural shift to acknowledge and celebrate the vital role that teachers play in shaping future generations. Furthermore, the study's findings offer valuable insights into the obstacles hindering teacher empowerment and highlight the importance of addressing these issues. By focusing on the need for effective support, professional development, and leadership, the study could encourage

school leaders to foster a more empowering environment for teachers. Additionally, the results may serve as a basis for drafting policies and recommendations aimed at tackling the challenges teachers face, ensuring they have the resources and support needed for success. These initiatives can support teachers and school leaders in overcoming empowerment barriers, leading to more engaged and effective educators. To ensure wide dissemination and accessibility of the research work on teacher empowerment, the study's findings will be disseminated within the schools in the 1st District, Koronadal City Division through meetings, seminars, trainings, and workshops. Additionally, the researcher intends to present the findings at local, national, and international research conferences, forums, and summits, reaching a broader audience. Furthermore, recognizing the importance of open access to research, the researcher will explore the possibility of online publication to facilitate easy access and wide dissemination of the study's findings on teacher empowerment.

1.1. Purpose of the Study—The purpose of my narrative research study is to explore the perspectives of public elementary school teachers on teacher empowerment and the challenges they face in their professional roles. My study aims to uncover the perceptions of public elementary school teachers in the Koronadal Central Elementary School, District 1, Koronadal City Division. Specifically, it will examine how these teachers perceive the challenges, strategies, and practices related to teacher empowerment in their schools. Moreover, my study aspires to develop a deeper understanding of the lessons learned from the insights gathered. The findings from my study could offer a valuable contribution by providing awareness into the importance of thoroughly exploring public elementary school teachers' experiences with teacher empowerment. By focusing on individual stories, the study can capture the nuanced challenges teachers face, and how these experiences influence their professional development. This approach will provide important context for enhancing teacher empowerment and improving the overall teaching environment for educators in the district. This study will be beneficial to the learners by providing teachers with a deeper understanding of their professional empowerment needs, leading to more contextualized and effective instruction. Teachers will gain valuable insights into the strategies and challenges they face in achieving empowerment, enabling them to refine their practices and better support learners. School leaders can use the findings to inform leadership strategies, professional development, and resource allocation to enhance teacher empowerment outcomes. Parents will benefit by gaining a clearer understanding of how teacher empowerment impacts their children's education, empowering them to support educators' efforts at home. Additionally, the study contributes to the body of knowledge for educational researchers and provides valuable insights for policymakers to improve teacher empowerment initiatives in schools. By taking into account the personal experiences of elementary school teachers in their journey toward empowerment, educational leaders can identify effective practices and adjust interventions and opportunities to address the unique challenges in their respective institutions. The findings may influence policy decisions and guide resource allocation, paving the way for strengthened teacher empowerment practices in public elementary schools. These efforts will offer teachers, particularly in provinces, increased access to professional development programs. Such initiatives aim to equip educators with essential tools and support to enhance learning outcomes for their learners.

1.2. Research Questions—This study will be conducted with the purpose of understanding the views on teacher empowerment of the teachers in public elementary schools. The course of

this study will be set by the following specific research inquiries:

- (1) What are the lived experiences of public elementary school teachers as forefront of educational advancement?
- (2) How do teachers cope with challenges as forefront of educational advancements?
- (3) What educational implications can be derived from the study's results?

1.3. Theoretical Lens—This study is anchored on the Psychological Empowerment Theory by Spreitzer (1995) provides a comprehensive framework for understanding teacher empowerment in educational settings. It focuses on four key elements: meaning, competence, self-determination, and impact. Teachers feel empowered when they find their work meaningful, have confidence in their abilities, are given autonomy in decision-making, and perceive that their efforts positively influence student outcomes. By fostering these dimensions, school administrators can enhance teacher engagement, motivation, and overall job satisfaction. Within the educational setting, this theory emphasizes the importance of creating a supportive environment where teachers' work is valued and their professional growth is prioritized. When educational leaders provide opportunities for teachers to enhance their skills, encourage their decision-making autonomy, and acknowledge their contributions, it leads to a more empowered teaching workforce. Teacher empowerment, according to this theory, directly influences teachers' commitment and fulfillment, ultimately fostering a thriving and productive educational community. The study is also strongly supported by Self-Determination Theory by Deci Ryan, (2000). This theory emphasizes the importance of intrinsic motivation and autonomy in fostering an individual's growth and well-being. It suggests that when teachers have more control over their work, they feel more empowered, leading to higher job satisfaction, improved teaching practices, and better outcomes for learners. From my viewpoint as the researcher, Self-Determination Theory emphasizes that teachers' intrinsic motivation

and autonomy are crucial in developing their empowerment. I see this as essential because when teachers feel competent, autonomous, and connected to their work, they are more likely to be engaged and committed to their roles. In the approach to teacher empowerment, prioritizing strategies that enhance teachers' sense of autonomy and competence can significantly increase their job satisfaction and effectiveness. By fostering an environment that supports these elements, school leaders can create a more motivated and empowered teaching workforce. This study also get its strength in the Critical Pedagogy Theory by Freire (1970). This theory advocates for a democratic and participatory approach to education, where teachers are seen as co-creators of knowledge rather than mere transmitters. This empowerment-oriented approach encourages teachers to reflect critically on their practices and engage in collective action to improve educational outcomes, making it a foundational theory for teacher empowerment. It is particularly relevant in teacher empowerment, as it emphasizes the importance of teachers engaging in a collaborative, reflective process to transform their teaching practices and advocate for social justice within education. This aligns with my belief that teacher empowerment is best fostered when educators are encouraged to critically analyze and challenge the structures that influence their teaching environment. By promoting dialogue and collective action among teachers, I am confident that it will foster a deeper sense of professional autonomy and commitment, ultimately enhancing their effectiveness and job satisfaction. Encouraging teachers to reflect on their roles within the educational system can empower them to

Fig. 1. The Conceptual Framework of the Study

create more equitable and impactful learning experiences for their learners. The conceptual framework of the study is presented in figure 1. Based on the figure, there are two interconnected variables. These variables are the lived experiences of public elementary school teachers on teacher empowerment as they relate to educational advancement. In the right circle is coping mechanisms teachers employ to navigate

the educational system and advance professionally. This includes strategies and approaches they use to overcome obstacles and achieve their goals. Lastly, the area where the circles intersect represents the educational insights drawn from the study. This is the core area of research findings, revealing the connections between teachers' experiences, their coping strategies, and the overall impact on their professional growth.

2. Methodology

This chapter of the study presented the methodology, research participants, data collection, role of the researcher, data analysis, trustworthiness of the study and the ethical consideration. Exploring facts and knowledge in this study necessitates the consequent design and implementation as elaborated in this chapter. In this study, the qualitative method that is appropriate to be applied are participant observation and in-depth interviews. Each method is particularly suited for obtaining a specific type of data. Participant observation is appropriate for collecting data on naturally occurring behavior in their usual contexts. In-depth Interview is optimal for collecting data on individuals' personal histories, perspectives, and experiences, particularly when sensitive topics are being explored. As a pragmatist, I use qualitative inquiry to investigate human lived experiences in order to describe their individual encounters with teacher empowerment in the context of educational practices. The description of the phenomenon explores what individuals experience and how they interpret these experiences (Creswell, 2020). Additionally, qualitative inquiry provides a rich and nuanced understanding of the complex dimensions of human consciousness. Through in-depth interviews, observations, and analysis of lived experiences, it helps unravel the complexities of teacher empowerment, shedding light on the subjective aspects of educators' professional lives.

2.1. Philosophical Assumptions—The philosophical assumptions of this study form the foundation for collecting, analyzing, and interpreting data in the context of teacher empowerment. These assumptions establish the guiding principles that influence the conclusions and decisions made throughout the research process. These principles, which vary in nature, are crucial for conducting rigorous research, beginning with the selection of the research topic, problem, or focus area, and aligning with a specific research paradigm. Stanage (1987) traces the idea of a "paradigm" to its Greek and Latin roots, where it signifies a model or example that shapes actions. In essence, a paradigm reflects the adoption of a specific perspective or worldview. Supporting this idea, Denzin and Lincoln (2000) describe a research paradigm as a "basic set of beliefs that guide action," addressing the core principles or worldview of the researcher. In the case of a study on teacher empowerment, these philosophical assumptions and paradigms guide how the research will explore and understand the experiences of teachers, emphasizing their roles, autonomy, and professional growth within the educational setting. In the context of teacher empowerment, these philosophical assumptions are vital. They shape the researcher's perspective on how teacher empowerment should be understood, implemented, and evaluated. For instance, a constructivist paradigm may guide the study by emphasizing the role of teachers' prior experiences and their interactions with educational practices, while a pragmatic paradigm might focus on practical strategies to enhance teacher empowerment in real-world school settings. Thus, the choice of paradigm directly influences the methodology and interpretation of findings, ensuring that the study aligns with a coherent worldview about teacher autonomy, professional growth, and empowerment within the educational system.

Ontology This part of the research pertains to how the issue relates to the nature of reality. According to Creswell (2020), reality is subjective and multiple, as seen by the participants in the study. The ontological issue addresses the nature of reality for the qualitative researcher, suggesting that reality is constructed by the individuals involved in the research situation. Therefore, multiple realities exist, such as those of the researcher, the individuals being investigated, and the readers or audiences interpreting the study. In this study, the experiences of public elementary school teachers regarding teacher empowerment are discussed by the participants, exploring their challenges and potential opportunities to effectively enhance their professional roles and autonomy in addressing the developmental needs of learners. In this study, the researcher will rely on the voices and interpretations of the participants through extensive quotes and themes that reflect their words, providing evidence of diverse perspectives on teacher empowerment. The responses of the participants will be coded and analyzed to identify both commonalities and distinct differences in their experiences and views. To ensure the reliability of the results, the participants' responses will be carefully coded and examined. Throughout the process, the researcher will maintain the authenticity of the responses, avoiding personal biases to ensure that the study accurately reflects the participants' experiences with teacher empowerment.

Epistemology This refers to the awareness of how knowledge claims are justified by staying as close to the participants as possible during the study to obtain firsthand information. Creswell and Poth (2018) state that a narrative type of qualitative study focuses on the stories and personal experiences of individuals to understand their perspectives, meanings, and insights. This approach will allow the researcher to explore how people make sense of their lives and experiences through narratives, providing rich, detailed data that can reveal deeper insights into specific phenomena. The researcher identified narrative study with the use of thematic analysis as the best means for this type of study. In this regard, the researcher holds an explicit belief. The intention of this study

is to gather information from the participants or teachers in public elementary schools in the 1st District, Koronadal City Division, on their perceived experiences with the challenges, approaches, and opportunities related to teacher empowerment.

Axiology It refers to the role of values in research. Creswell (2020) affirms that the role of values in a study is significant. It suggests that the researcher openly discusses values that shape the narrative and includes their interpretation in conjunction with the interpretation of participants. Upholding the dignity and value of every detail of information obtain from the participants will be ensured by the researcher. The researcher understands the personal and value-laden nature of information gathered from the study. Therefore, the researcher will preserve the merit of the participants' answers and carefully interpret the answers in the light of the participants' interpretation. **Rhetoric** It means that reporting what reality is through the eyes of the research participants. This is important because it means that the research would report objectively on what was observed and heard from the participants. This research study will use personal voice and qualitative terms and limited definition. In the context of the study, the researcher will use the first person in interpretation of the experiences of public elementary school teachers on teacher empowerment.

2.2. Qualitative Assumptions—Methodology is a creative and responsive approach to understanding questions and subject matter, while the method refers to the specific knowledge and procedures used (Gerodias, 2013). In this study, the challenges, approaches, and opportunities in teacher empowerment as experienced by public elementary school teachers in Koronadal Central Elementary Schools, District 1, Koronadal

City Division, will be gathered through their personal narratives. The researcher's effort to understand the perspectives of public elementary school teachers regarding their issues/challenges and opportunities on teacher empowerment will serve as the foundation for this qualitative research. Gerodias (2013) emphasizes that such an approach is valuable for uncovering the meanings and motivations behind cultural symbols, personal experiences, and phenomena.

2.3. Design and Procedure—This research utilized the narrative research approach to allow researcher to explore how people make sense of their lives and experiences through narratives, providing rich, detailed data that can reveal deeper insights into specific phenomena. The purpose of the narrative research approach is to focus on understanding and exploring the stories individuals tell about their personal experiences.

It emphasizes how people make sense of their lives and identities through narratives, allowing researchers to analyze the meaning and context behind these stories. Typically involving a small number of participants, this method seeks to capture detailed, in-depth accounts that reveal unique perspectives. The goal is to understand how individuals interpret and construct their experiences within specific social, cultural, and historical contexts (Creswell Poth, 2018).

2.4. Research Participants—This narrative research study involved a smaller group of participants. The sample size in this qualitative study were sufficient to capture the diverse

perspectives and experiences of the participants. By collecting in-depth, rich insights into their lived experiences, this study explored how public elementary school teachers make sense of

their empowerment through storytelling. This approach allows for a deeper, more contextualized understanding of the personal and social realities of teacher empowerment, which might be missed through other research methods. It also emphasized the voices of participants, highlighting their unique viewpoints and fostering a connection between their experiences and broader educational or societal issues (Creswell Poth, 2018). Purposive sampling was employed to identify the participants for this study. Purposive sampling is a non-probability sampling method where participants are selected based on specific characteristics relevant to the research objectives. This method, also known as selective or subjective sampling, allows the researcher to choose participants who provide valuable insights based on their experiences. The researcher selected eight public elementary

school teachers from Koronadal Central Elementary School, District 1, Koronadal City Division, who have relevant experience in teacher empowerment. The inclusion criteria for the participants are as follows: currently employed as permanent public elementary school teachers in Koronadal Central Elementary School, District 1, Koronadal City Division for 5 years and more. The data gathered was used to identify emerging themes and patterns based on their personal narratives. The researcher employed the purposive sampling design since the participants is chosen based on the criteria or purpose of the study (Creswell, 2020). It is also known as judgmental, selective or subjective sampling. The selection of the participants was purposefully done to ensure that the findings would be authentic (Marshall, 1996).

2.5. Ethical Considerations—The ethical considerations are significant in the design of this research study. The researcher needed to consider several ethical issues about the research participant in this fieldwork. Ethical considerations can be specified as one of the most important parts of the research. The researcher needs to adhere to promote the aims of the research imparting authentic knowledge, truth and prevention of error. Social Value This research study is very essential to the educational society. In this study, the social value will be focused on the experiences of teachers. This study was specifically conducted among the public elementary school teachers. This study also serve as a basis for the higher authorities to create more programs and resolutions where public elementary school teachers could benefit. Thus, the social problem that pushes the interest of the researcher is the challenges faced by the public elementary school teachers on teacher empowerment. Informed Consent In the conduct and practice of this study, the Treaty Principle of

Participation as cited by McLeod (2013) was adhered to. The invitation to the participants ensured that their participation in the research was completely voluntary in nature, and is based on the understanding of adequate information. The participant recruitment and selection lodged in the appendices of this study. Gaining the trust and support of research participants is critical to the informed and ethical academic inquiry and phenomenological research (Pierre, 2012). All participants were given an informed consent form before scheduling the interviews and participating in the phenomenological research process. Each participant required to provide a signed personal acknowledgement, consent, and an indication of a willingness-to-participate-in-the-study release. The purpose of the informed consent letter is to introduce the research effort, provide contact information, articulate the intent of the study, request voluntary participation by the recipients, and anticipate the information that the informants were expected to provide. All participants were required to sign and return

the letter of consent to the researcher before participating in the research. Vulnerability of Research Participants The participants of this study were capable of answering the research instrument for they are all professional teachers in public elementary schools. Thus, the researcher will assure them that as the researcher, she can easily be reached through the contact number and address in case there are some clarifications or questions with regard to the study.

Risks, Benefits and Safety The recruitment of the respondents is free of coercion, undue influence or inducement. Moreover, respondents will be provided with the contact numbers of the chair of the panel or panel members in case they have queries related to the study. Further, the researcher will ensure that the respondents are safe during the conduct of the interview. Thus, the interview will be conducted in a safe venue and administered during their convenient time. Dominant concern of this study is the Treaty Principle of Protection, as reflected in the respect for the rights of privacy and confidentiality, and minimization of risk. This will be done by assigning pseudonyms for each informant so as not to disclose their identity. The possibility of a degree of risk inherent to this will be minimized through taking all reasonable steps to guarantee participant confidentiality. **Privacy and Confidentiality of Information** This study will observe the Data Privacy Act of 2002 to assure that the data cannot be traced back to their real sources to protect participants' identities. Thus, utmost care was taken to ensure anonymity of the data sources. Hence, any printed output that were carried-out from this study and kept in anonymity. Further, all the issues were given considerations so that there will be no conflict of interest among the researcher and the respondents. Any type of misleading information, as well as representation of primary data findings in a biased way will be avoided. **Justice** The respondents were informed of the researcher's role and their corresponding role

during data gathering. They were briefed that they have to give their full honesty in answering the survey questions and additionally, any type of communication in relation to the research should be done with honesty. Similarly, they were informed that they were the ones to benefit first with the results of the study. **Transparency** The results of the study can be accessed by the respondents and the school principal of the participating school because the information is available, and placed in electronic storage devices in which can be requested from the researcher to provide. In addition, by learning on the results of the study, public elementary school teachers were aware of the significance of the study and its contribution to their well-being as educators. Further, each of the participants was advised that they have the right to withdraw their information at any time up to the completion of the data collection process, and that they can be requested and allowed to verify their individual transcript after the interview is carried out. This provided the participants with the opportunity to amend, or remove any information which they feel might identify them. The researcher reserved the right to employ the use of pseudonyms, and changing names and or non-significant dates in the interest of the protection of the identity of the participant in all subsequent data analysis and reporting. **Qualification of the Researcher** The researcher ensured that she possesses the needed qualification to conduct the study. The researcher completed the academic requirements, passed the comprehensive examination prior to thesis writing which is the last requirement to obtain the masteral degree, and that the researcher is qualified to conduct the study physically, mentally, emotionally and financially. In addition, the advisee-adviser tandem ensured that the study will reach its completion. **Adequacy of Facilities** The researcher strived that the study can be completed successfully on the specified time and that he or she is equipped with the necessary resources.

Likewise, the technical committee help in the enhancement of the paper by giving the needed suggestions and recommendations for the improvement of the study. Also, the researcher will ensure that she has enough funds to continue and finish the research. Thus, this study is hoped to be completed on the target time.

Community Involvement The researcher show respect to the local tradition, culture and views of the respondents in this study. Moreover, this study will not involve any use of deceit in any stage of its implementation, and specifically, in the recruitment of the participants, or methods of data collection. Furthermore, the

researcher will necessarily express great pleasure for the wholehearted participation of the interviewees in the conduct of the study. Plagiarism and Fabrication as the Researcher The researcher respects other works by properly citing the author and rewrite what someone else has said his or her own way. The researcher also use quotes to indicate that the text has been taken from another paper. Similarly, the researcher assured that honesty is present in working the manuscript and no intentional misrepresentation and making up of data or results is included, or purposefully put forward conclusions that are not accurate.

*2.6. Role of the Researcher—*My responsibility is to uncover, transfer and undertake knowledge for the benefit of educational institutions. To do so, as the researcher, I took-up the following roles in the course of the study: Facilitator and Promoter of Unbiased Research I conducted interview to the participants and guide them in the process. I interpreted ideas and responses base on existing literature and related studies and not on my own knowledge, thoughts and feelings to avoid the intrusion of bias. Expert in Qualitative Method I implemented the narrative qualitative method correctly. To do so, as the researcher, I assessed myself and seeks help to my research adviser and other research professionals. These help me exhibit competence in explaining the study without biasing the participants, conducting interview properly according to the design, making appropriate field observations, selecting appropriate artifacts, images, and journal portions, employing Thematic Content Analysis precisely. Collector and Keeper of Data I ensured different ways of making a record of what is said and done during the interview, such as taking handwritten notes

or audio and/or video recording. The recordings were transcribed verbatim before data analysis can begin. Records done by me was properly secured as they contain sensitive information and are relevant to the research. However, the data that were collected, a primary responsibility of the researcher is to safeguard participants and their data. Mechanisms for such safeguarding must be clearly articulated to participants and must be approved by a relevant research ethics review board before the research begins. Analyst of Data I look at the phenomenon or problem from the participants' perspective by interpreting data, transcribing and checking, reading between the lines, coding and theming. I made sure that the findings are true to the participants and that their voices are heard. Organizer and Presenter of Data I presented the problem and the related literatures and studies that support it. Findings of the study was presented too by research question – stating the results for each one by using themes to show how the research questions were answered in the study. Moreover, future directions and implications of the study are given for improvement of educational policy and practices.

2.7. Data Collection—

The following are the step-by-step process of gathering the data needed. Securing Endorsement from the Dean of Graduate School The researcher asked an endorsement from the Dean of Graduate School of Rizal Memorial Colleges as one of the documents needed for submission to the office of the Schools Division Superintendent in asking permission to conduct study. Asking Permission from the Schools Division Superintendent The researcher asked permission from the Schools Division Superintendent of Koronadal City Division to conduct the study in the identified school. The researcher also sent a letter addressed to the Schools Division Superintendent with the attached Chapter 1 and 2 together with the research instrument which explains the objectives of the study and the identification of the participants. The researcher waited for the response of the SDS before the conduct of it. Asking Permission from the School Principal After securing the approval of the SDS, the researcher sent letter to the school principal of Koronadal Central Elementary School explaining about the study to be conducted in the said school. Obtaining Consent from the Participants The researcher ask permission from the partic-

ipants. They were formally oriented about the study and of the process they shall go through as participants.

Conducting the Interview The researcher conducted the in-depth interview using the interview questionnaire. The profile of the participants was taken, jot down notes, and conversations will be recorded using a sound recorder for ease of transcription. The researcher will carefully listen and respond actively during the interviews. Transcribing the Responses of the Interviewees The researcher transcribed the responses of the interviewees precisely by recalling their answers from the sound recorder. If the participants used their vernacular language, the researcher translated it to English language. Data Coding and Thematic Content Analysis After the transcription, the data then be categorized and coded. Then, themes is extracted and individual data within the participants was compared and contrasted. Additional information was gathered if the need arises and was examined thoroughly and integrate it into the existing body of data. After which, data will be compared and contrasted between the participants in order to come up with patterns and trends.

2.8. *Data Analysis*—In this study, thematic analysis was utilized to analyze the gathered data. The researcher analyzed the answers of the participants from the conducted interviews with the use of Creswell's Model specifically the identifying of themes approach. According to Creswell (2020) themes in qualitative research are similar codes aggregated together to form a major idea in the database. Familiarization With the data is common to all forms of qualitative analysis, the researcher will immerse herself in, and become intimately familiar with, their data; reading and re-reading the data and noting any initial analytic observations. Coding Is also a common element of many approaches to qualitative analysis, involves generating pithy

labels for important features of the data of relevance to the broad research question guiding the analysis. Coding is not simply a method of data reduction; it is also an analytic process, so codes capture both a semantic and conceptual reading of the data. The researcher will code every data item and ends this phase by collating all their codes and relevant data extracts. Searching for Themes Is coherent and meaningful pattern in the data relevant to the research question. The researcher ended this phase by collating all the coded data relevant to each theme. Reviewing Themes The researcher reflected on whether the themes tell a convincing and compelling story about the data, and began to define the nature of each individual theme, and the relationship

between the themes. For these, Thematic Content Analysis was employed by the researcher. Thematic Content Analysis is a descriptive presentation of qualitative data in which a detailed analysis of each theme will be made by identifying the ‘essence’ of each theme and construct-

ing a concise, punchy and informative name for each theme (Andersen, 2013). Writing-up involves weaving together the analytic narrative and data extracts to tell the reader a coherent and persuasive story about the data, and contextualizing it in relation to existing literature.

2.9. Framework of Analysis—The framework analysis of this research will be flexible to allow researcher to either collect all the data and then analyze it or do data analysis during the collection process. In the analysis stage the gathered data is sifted, charted, and sorted in accordance with key issues and themes. This study employs qualitative research method. Rigorous and systematic steps will be observed in analyzing the information gathered from the teacher-participants. Data analyzed following the steps outlined by O’Connor and Gibson

(2003) on qualitative data analysis: Organizing the Data Data are organized in a way that is easy to look at and that allows the researcher to go through each topic to pick out concepts and themes. Finding and Organizing Ideas and Concepts Find specific words or ideas keep coming up then organize these ideas into codes or categories. Building Over-Arching Themes in the Data Each of the response categories has one or more associated themes that give a deeper meaning to the data. Different categories can be collapsed under one main over-arching theme.

2.10. Trustworthiness of the Study—Trustworthiness is all about establishing credibility, transferability, confirmability and dependability. In qualitative study, trustworthiness is very important because the result and finding of the research study would depend on the process of how it was being conducted by the researcher. Trustworthiness of a research study is important to evaluating its worth. Due to the nature of qualitative study, honesty in all the data and details are required. Trustworthiness makes the researcher’s study worthy to read, share, and be proud of. Credibility Was how confident the qualitative researcher is in the truth of the research study’s findings. The researcher in this study believed that honesty in everything you do was essential to attain worthwhile success. The researcher has no derogatory records or administrative issues which ruin her integrity. Lincoln and Guba (2000) state that credibility refers to the idea of internal consistency, where the main issue was “how we ensure rigor in the

research process and how we communicate to others that we have done so.” Transferability Refers to how the qualitative researcher demonstrates the applicability of the study’s findings to other contexts. In this case, “other contexts” can refer to similar situations, populations, or phenomena. The researcher will examine the effects of issues, challenges, and opportunities related to teacher empowerment. A narrative study on the perspectives of public elementary school teachers regarding their experiences with teacher empowerment is essential because it provides a rich, personal understanding of their real-life experiences in different educational settings. By collecting their insights, this method emphasizes the specific strategies teachers use to navigate challenges and leverage opportunities in nurturing empowerment, especially within public elementary schools. The findings can inform educational policies, teacher empowerment initiatives, and professional development programs, ensuring that the challenges, strate-

Fig. 2. Analytical Framework of the Study

gies, and opportunities faced by teachers in their empowerment journey are acknowledged and effectively addressed. Confirmability Is the degree of neutrality in the research study's findings. In other words, this means that the findings will be based on participants' responses and not any potential bias or personal motivations of the researcher. This involves making sure that researcher does not skew the interpretation of what the research participants said to fit a certain narrative. The information using the audit trail in this situation is thoughtfully recorded by the researcher which highlights every step of data analysis that was made in order to provide a rationale for the decisions made. This helps establish that the research study's findings accurately portray participants' responses. Morrow (2005) states that confirmability was based on the acknowledgement that research is never objective. Dependability Is the extent

that the study could be repeated by other researchers and that the findings would be consistent. In other words, if a person wanted to replicate your study, they should have enough information from your research report to do so and obtain similar findings as your study did. A qualitative researcher used inquiry audit in order to establish dependability which requires an outside person to review and examine the research process and the data analysis in order to ensure that the findings are consistent and could be repeated. In this component, the use of database was very important in backing up information collected and noting changes for all types of research studies. All the data collected was properly kept for future use as references. Morrow (2005) stated that dependability deals with the core issue that "the way in which a study is conducted should be consistent across time, researchers, and analysis techniques."

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Experiences and Challenges of Teachers as Forefront of Educational Advancement—Teachers play a central role in driving educational progress, as they directly shape classroom practices, learner engagement, and the implementation of reforms. Their experiences serve as valuable insights into what works in education and what hinders progress. As the primary agents of instruction, teachers are expected to adapt to evolving curricula, integrate technology, and respond to diverse learner needs—all while maintaining high standards of teaching. Understanding their lived experiences is essential for designing policies and systems that truly

support educational advancement. Despite their pivotal role, teachers often face significant challenges such as limited resources, administrative pressures, and a lack of professional support. These obstacles can hinder their ability to innovate and lead meaningful change in their classrooms and schools. The mismatch between expectations and the support they receive can result in burnout, reduced motivation, and decreased instructional quality. Addressing these challenges is crucial to empowering teachers as leaders of transformation and ensuring that educational reforms lead to real, lasting impact in learner outcomes.

3.1.1. Resource Constraints and Workload Pressures—Teachers face significant challenges related to limited resources and increasing workload pressures, which impact their ability to deliver quality education. Budget constraints

often lead to scarcity of teaching materials essential for effective lesson delivery. This limitation forces educators to improvise or reduce the scope of activities, which can compromise the learning experience. Additionally, the heavy

workload, characterized by administrative tasks, lesson planning, and extra-curricular responsibilities, contributes to teacher burnout and stress. Many participants expressed difficulty in balancing professional duties with personal life, highlighting the emotional and physical toll of these demands. Resource scarcity and workload pressures highlight the complex realities teachers navigate daily. Addressing these issues requires systemic support to ensure teachers are equipped and supported, promoting both their well-being and professional effectiveness. Ahmadi (2022) highlights how budget limitations significantly affect the quality of instruction in schools. Due to insufficient funding, teachers are often compelled to rely on makeshift or improvised materials to deliver their lessons. This lack of adequate resources not only hampers the effectiveness of instruction but also limits the learning opportunities available to students. The study underscores how financial constraints directly impact teaching quality, linking it closely to the broader issue of resource scarcity. Likewise, Mangindalat (2022) echoes similar concerns regarding the unavailability of teaching materials in many educational settings. Teachers are frequently forced to be resourceful, using limited or outdated materials to meet curricu-

3.1.2. Diverse Student Needs and Classroom Management—Teachers managing large and heterogeneous classrooms face challenges in addressing varied learning styles and socio-economic backgrounds. Classroom management becomes more complex as educators strive to accommodate diverse behaviors and special needs within a single setting. This diversity requires adaptive teaching strategies to ensure inclusive participation and effective learning. Effective classroom management and differentiated instruction are critical in addressing the needs of a diverse student population. Teachers' adaptive approaches play a vital role in creating an inclusive and supportive learning environ-

ment. This improvisation, while creative, can compromise the depth and richness of learning experiences. Such conditions illustrate the persistent challenges posed by inadequate educational resources in delivering instruction, planning lessons, managing classrooms, and fulfilling administrative duties create a taxing environment for educators. This overwhelming workload not only affects teachers' health and well-being but also diminishes their instructional effectiveness. The study reinforces how workload pressures are a critical factor in the overall performance and morale of teachers. Collie (2021) brings attention to the heavy workload that teachers endure, which often leads to burnout and heightened stress levels. The demands of Similarly, Baloran and Hernan (2020) explore the difficulty teachers face in balancing professional responsibilities with personal life demands. The challenge of meeting both sets of obligations require strong resilience and effective time management, which not all educators are equipped to maintain. These pressures, if unmanaged, can lead to emotional exhaustion and reduced productivity. Their findings align with the theme by emphasizing how personal and professional role conflicts exacerbate the stress linked to workload and limited resources

Singh and Singla (2023) emphasize the complexities teachers encounter when managing large and diverse classrooms. With learners coming from various socio-economic backgrounds and possessing different learning styles, educators must continuously adjust their instructional methods. This diversity increases the demand for differentiated teaching approaches to ensure that all learners are engaged and supported. Their study underscores how student diversity significantly challenges classroom management and instructional effectiveness. While, Erdogan and Cavl (2019) focus on the necessity for flexible and inclusive classroom management strategies to accommodate a wide range of

student behaviors and special needs. Teachers must respond to the unique emotional, cognitive, and behavioral profiles of learners, often without specialized support or resources. Creating a learning environment that is both structured

3.1.3. Emotional and Professional Demands—Teaching demands significant emotional labor, especially as teachers balance high expectations from stakeholders with their own professional and personal well-being. Sustaining motivation and passion amid stress and burnout remains a persistent challenge. The emotional strain and professional demands faced by teachers underscore the importance of establishing strong support systems. These systems should prioritize teacher well-being and help maintain motivation amid daily challenges. Fostering such support is essential for sustaining educators' passion and long-term commitment to the profession. Fernandez and Quines (2023) shed light on the significant emotional strain teachers endure as they respond to the expectations of various stakeholders, including parents, school leaders, and the community. Educators are often expected to remain motivated and perform consistently, even in the face of limited support and persistent challenges. This emotional burden can accumulate over time, affecting their overall well-being and job satisfaction. The study illustrates how stakeholder pressure contributes to the growing emotional demands placed on teaching professionals. Further, Johnson et al. (2019) emphasize the ongoing challenge educators face in maintaining emotional resilience within their profession. The constant need to inspire and support learners while handling administrative and instructional tasks can

3.2. Coping Mechanisms and Strategies for Teacher Empowerment—In the face of increasing educational demands, teachers must develop effective coping mechanisms to maintain

and inclusive requires skillful adaptation and a deep understanding of individual student needs. Their findings highlight how addressing behavioral diversity is a vital component of effective classroom management.

be mentally exhausting. Teachers must often suppress personal stress to remain effective in the classroom. Their research highlights how the emotional labor of teaching is a crucial, yet often overlooked, aspect of professional demands. Furthermore, Collie (2021) points to the importance of achieving a healthy work-life balance to sustain teachers' emotional health and long-term commitment to the profession. Without adequate balance, the risk of burnout increases, potentially leading to disengagement and a decline in teaching quality. Nurturing personal well-being is essential for maintaining the enthusiasm and passion required in such a demanding career. This reinforces how personal care is intricately linked to managing the emotional and professional pressures of teaching. From a researcher's perspective, teachers require systematic support from school heads and DepEd officials, particularly when implementing learner-focused programs or remediation strategies aimed at improving well-being and professional effectiveness. Managing heterogeneous classrooms presents significant challenges in classroom management; learners exhibit diverse behaviors, and some may be non-readers. Without employing strategies tailored to individual abilities and capabilities, achieving lesson plan objectives becomes difficult. While diverse learner behaviors pose challenges, teachers should strive to foster improvement and positive change in their students' lives.

their well-being and professional effectiveness. Strategies such as self-care, time management, peer collaboration, and reflective practice help educators manage stress and maintain a sense

Fig. 3. Emerging themes on the Experiences and Challenges of Teachers as Forefront of Educational Advancement

of control over their work. These coping approaches not only protect against burnout but also reinforce teachers' confidence and autonomy. Empowered teachers who actively use such strategies are more resilient and better equipped to navigate the challenges of the profession. Beyond individual practices, institutional strategies also play a critical role in supporting teacher empowerment. Access to continuous professional development, supportive

leadership, and collaborative learning environments enhances teachers' capacity to cope and thrive. When schools implement systems that acknowledge teacher voice and provide targeted support, educators are more likely to feel valued and motivated. These organizational strategies are essential for building a culture of empowerment that sustains teacher leadership and drives educational improvement.

3.2.1. Professional Development and Training—Teachers emphasized the importance of continuous professional development through seminars, workshops, and training sessions. These opportunities help them enhance their skills and integrate innovative teaching methods, including technology, to improve instructional quality. Professional development plays a crucial role in empowering teachers by enhancing their knowledge and instructional

abilities. It provides educators with updated strategies and tools to deliver engaging and impactful lessons. Through continuous learning, teachers become more confident and effective in addressing the diverse needs of their learners. Kilag and Abendan (2023) emphasize that active participation in seminars, workshops, and ongoing professional learning is vital for empowering teachers and enhancing their competencies. These opportunities enable educators

to stay current with educational trends, refine their teaching strategies, and build confidence in their practice. Continuous learning fosters professional growth, equipping teachers with

3.2.2. Support Systems and Collaboration—Support from colleagues, supervisors, and family serves as a key strategy for coping with the demands of teaching. Collaboration enables sharing of resources and expertise, while leadership opportunities foster empowerment and active engagement in school improvement. Robust support networks and collaborative relationships help teachers build resilience. These connections provide encouragement and shared strategies that empower educators in their practice. As a result, teachers are better equipped to overcome challenges and continue thriving in their profession. Ecarma (2024) emphasized the vital role of support systems in fostering teachers' professional resilience. When educators face challenges in their practice, they often turn to colleagues, supervisors, and family for encouragement and guidance. This network of support helps them manage stress and sustain their motivation to teach. Such interactions highlight how emotional and professional backing can serve as a foundation for teacher well-being and effectiveness. Blanco et al. (2022) highlight the power of collaboration through the sharing of resources and teaching strategies among educators. By engaging in collaborative learning environments, teachers not only gain new insights but also feel empowered in their roles. This exchange fosters a culture of mutual support and continuous professional development. Their findings stressed the importance of associate collaboration in enhancing instructional quality and fostering a sense of belonging within the teaching community. Personal Well-being and Resilience Practices. Teachers adopt personal well-being practices such as relaxation, travel, and meditation to maintain mental health

the skills needed to meet evolving classroom demands. Their study underscores how professional development serves as a foundation for effective and empowered teaching.

and resilience. Maintaining a positive mindset, faith, and adaptability supports their ability to face professional challenges with strength. Focusing on personal well-being and resilience helps teachers maintain their energy and enthusiasm for teaching. These practices support their ability to handle the pressures of the profession. As a result, educators remain motivated and effective, even in challenging educational settings. Mahendri et al. (2022) stressed the importance of self-care activities in nurturing teacher resilience. Practices such as relaxation, personal reflection, and mental health promotion allow educators to recharge and maintain emotional balance. These activities serve as protective factors against burnout and help sustain long-term well-being. Their study highlights how intentional self-care is a vital component of personal resilience for teachers. Similarly, Mualim (2022) underscores the significance of maintaining faith, adaptability, and a positive mindset in managing occupational stress. These inner strengths enable teachers to respond constructively to the demands of their profession. By cultivating optimism and spiritual grounding, educators are better equipped to face adversity. This perspective aligns closely with resilience practices rooted in personal values and emotional regulation. From a researcher's perspective, teachers should know how to manage stress and control their workload, especially when facing excessive demands and pressure. I manage my own stress through self-care practices such as eating ice cream, massage therapy, and spending time with family. Effective time management is also crucial to avoid accumulating work and meeting deadlines. Peer collaboration with colleagues, school administrators,

Fig. 4. Emerging Themes on the Coping Mechanisms and Strategies for Teacher Empowerment

friends, and family can help distribute the demands of teaching. Furthermore, teachers are empowered by attending training and seminars

to enhance their skills and develop innovative teaching strategies for more effective lesson delivery.

3.3. Educational Insights and Implications of Teacher Empowerment—Teacher empowerment offers deep educational insights into how autonomy, professional trust, and support influence teaching effectiveness. When educators are given the authority to make instructional decisions and contribute to school policies, they feel a stronger sense of ownership and accountability. This sense of agency leads to more innovative, learner-centered practices that enhance classroom engagement and achievement. Understanding these dynamics is crucial for shaping educational systems that value teacher

leadership as a driver of meaningful change. The consequences of teacher empowerment extend beyond individual professional growth to the broader goals of educational transformation. Empowered teachers are more likely to collaborate, mentor peers, and advocate for reforms that align with learner needs. Their involvement in decision-making processes strengthens school communities and supports a more inclusive, responsive education system. Thus, promoting teacher empowerment is not only a matter of equity and respect but also a strategic move toward sustainable improvement in teaching and learning outcomes.

3.3.1. Commitment to Professional Growth and Innovation—

Teachers' experiences underscored a strong commitment to ongoing professional growth and innovation as critical to their empowerment and educational advancement. Participants expressed enthusiasm for embracing lifelong learning to keep their knowledge and skills current, which enabled them to respond dynamically to changing curricula and student needs. Innovation was manifested in adopting new teaching strategies such as differentiated instruction and multimedia resources to engage diverse learners. Many teachers highlighted their openness to integrating emerging educational technologies, recognizing the benefits for student motivation and deeper learning. This dedication to professional development reflected teachers' belief in the importance of evolving practices that support student-centered learning and prepare learners for future challenges. Empowered teachers saw themselves as agents of change who continuously sought creative solutions to improve instruction and student outcomes. Ecarma (2024) highlighted the role of

continuous professional development in helping teachers navigate educational reforms. Through ongoing learning and innovation, educators become more responsive to diverse learner needs and more confident in implementing inclusive practices. This growth mindset not only enhances teaching strategies but also fuels a culture of lifelong learning. Ecarma's work emphasizes that sustained professional growth is key to staying relevant and effective in a changing educational landscape. Also, Risambessy, A. (2023) underscores the importance of teacher empowerment by ensuring access to appropriate training and essential resources. When educators are well-equipped and supported, they are more capable of adapting to new pedagogical demands and integrating innovative practices. This empowerment fosters a sense of ownership over their professional journey and encourages creativity in the classroom. Risambessy's findings reinforce the idea that investing in teachers' growth is crucial for educational advancement and lasting impact.

3.3.2. Impact on Teaching and Learning Outcomes—Teachers reported that empowerment through training, collaboration, and personal resilience positively influenced their classroom management and instructional effectiveness, ultimately enhancing learning outcomes. Participants observed that empowered teachers demonstrated improved ability to tailor instruction to the diverse needs and learning styles of their students. Enhanced classroom management led to a more conducive learning environment, reducing behavioral issues and increasing student engagement. Teachers also noted greater confidence in using differentiated strategies and technology to facilitate active participation and meaningful learning experiences. These impacts were linked to the broader goal of educational advancement, as empowered teachers contributed to developing learn-

ers' skills, motivation, and academic success. The findings suggest that teacher empowerment is a crucial factor in achieving positive teaching and learning outcomes. The findings of this study strongly align with Spreitzer's (1995) Psychological Empowerment Theory, particularly its four dimensions: meaning, competence, self-determination, and impact. Teachers in the study expressed a deep sense of purpose in their roles, highlighting how meaningful engagement with learners and shared decision-making enhanced their professional fulfillment. They demonstrated confidence in their instructional practices and actively sought collaborative opportunities, reflecting competence and self-determination. These experiences affirm that when educators are given autonomy and their contributions are valued, their sense of empowerment grows, leading to greater moti-

vation and commitment to educational advancement. Similarly, the results resonate with Deci and Ryan's (2000) Self-Determination Theory, as teachers reported feeling more empowered when granted control over their teaching methods and professional choices. The intrinsic motivation to improve learner outcomes and continuously grow in their roles was evident throughout their narratives. This autonomy not only increased their job satisfaction but also reinforced their sense of ownership in the educational process. The findings support the theory's premise that autonomy and intrinsic motivation are foundational to personal and professional empowerment in teaching. The findings of the study support the study of Overton Putra (2021), that emphasized that empowered teachers significantly enhance classroom dynamics and learner engagement. When educators feel confident and

supported, they are more likely to implement innovative strategies that captivate and motivate learners. This active engagement leads to better learning experiences and outcomes. Their research highlights that teacher empowerment is directly linked to the overall success of educational delivery. Moreover, Ratnasari Sudarma (2019) stressed the importance of reinforcing teacher empowerment initiatives to elevate teaching quality and learner performance. Access to professional development, decision-making opportunities, and supportive leadership fosters a sense of agency among teachers. As a result, empowered educators are more effective in addressing diverse learner needs and achieving academic goals. Their findings support the notion that empowering teachers is a critical factor in driving educational excellence.

3.3.3. Teacher Leadership and Agency in Educational Transformation—Empowering teachers nurtures leadership qualities and enhances their sense of agency, allowing them to take active roles in shaping curriculum, instruction, and school culture. When teachers are entrusted with decision-making and provided with opportunities for growth, they become catalysts for positive change within the educational system. This empowerment builds confidence and ownership, fostering a more motivated and innovative teaching force. As a result, empowered educators contribute significantly to meaningful and sustainable educational transformation. Teacher empowerment also creates a ripple effect that enhances learner engagement and academic success. Educators who feel supported and valued are more likely to implement inclusive and responsive teaching practices that meet diverse learner needs. This leads to improved classroom environments and stronger learning outcomes. Therefore, investing in teacher empowerment is not only essential for professional

development but also for ensuring equity and quality in education. In many educational settings, the lack of adequate resources and support systems significantly undermines teacher leadership and agency. Educators frequently encounter challenges in accessing essential teaching materials, technology, and classroom assistance—factors that are vital for delivering innovative and high-quality instruction. The findings of Ahmadi and Arief (2022) support this viewpoint, revealing that when such resources are lacking, teachers feel restricted in their ability to exercise professional creativity and autonomy. This not only limits their effectiveness but also weakens their role as proactive leaders in educational transformation. Additionally, the dominance of standardized testing and accountability demands continues to stifle teacher agency. When instructional priorities are dictated by test performance rather than by meaningful learning outcomes, teachers lose the freedom to design engaging, learner-centered experiences. Haryono et al. (2021) reinforce this perspective in

Fig. 5. Emerging themes on the Educational Insights and implications of Teacher Empowerment

their findings, showing that an overemphasis on metrics reduces teachers’ motivation and narrows their instructional focus. As a result, their potential to lead dynamic and transformative educational practices is significantly diminished. From a researcher’s perspective, I am highly motivated to teach when I can apply new and effective strategies like project based learning, gamification, flipped classroom and ideas that enhance student learning. Innovative strategies are especially important in heterogeneous classrooms to foster greater student responsiveness

and confidence. Heterogeneous classrooms provide context and strengthens the argument for innovative strategies. One effective approach is to enhance classroom activities using technology. Given that we live in the 21st century, students are already highly engaged with gadgets and social media; leveraging these tools and relevant applications can significantly increase engagement. A teacher’s passion and innovative teaching approach to improved learning outcomes in heterogeneous classroom setting.

4. Implications and Future Directions

In this chapter, I provided a comprehensive summary of the teachers’ empowerment journey toward educational advancements, drawing on the findings to discuss its implications and potential future pathways. The study aimed to explore the strategies teachers utilize to enhance their professional growth, the challenges they face in navigating their roles, and the valuable insights gained from their experiences. Employing a qualitative phenomenological approach with thematic analysis, and guided by Creswell’s (2020) framework, open-ended interviews were conducted to

capture an authentic and nuanced understanding of the educators lived experiences.

4.1. Findings—This approach enabled participants to candidly reflect on their personal and professional development throughout the empowerment process. Thematic analysis revealed that teachers encountered significant challenges, including limited access to necessary resources, increased responsibilities, and difficulties sustaining motivation and engagement. To overcome these hurdles, educators re-

4.2. Implications—The findings of this study carry significant implications for the broader educational system, particularly in advancing teacher empowerment within the Philippine context. The experiences and insights shared by public elementary school teachers in Koronadal Central Elementary School illuminate key structural, emotional, and institutional realities that shape their empowerment. The study marked the urgent need for systemic and sustained professional development. Teachers who feel supported through relevant training and upskilling opportunities demonstrate stronger classroom performance, confidence in integrating innovation, and commitment to lifelong learning. Thus, education authorities must invest in dynamic, context-responsive training aligned with teachers' actual challenges and aspirations. The research highlights how resource limitations and excessive workloads undermine empowerment, leading to stress, burnout, and reduced instructional quality. Addressing this requires a rethinking of teacher workload allocation, enhanced material support, and provision of teaching assistants, especially in resource-constrained schools. It reveals that empowered teachers serve as agents of educational transformation. Deci, E. and Ryan, R., developed the Self-Determination Theory. The author developed this theory of motivation, top-

lied on resourcefulness, collaboration with colleagues, continuous professional learning, and support from the community and parents. The findings underscore the critical importance of fostering adaptability, enhancing pedagogical practices, and strengthening cooperative relationships, all of which are essential components in the ongoing empowerment of teachers as catalysts for educational progress.

ping the dominant belief that the best way to get human beings to perform tasks is to reinforce their behavior with rewards. When given autonomy, recognition, and collaborative opportunities, they do not merely deliver instruction—they shape inclusive, learner-centered environments that foster academic and socio-emotional growth. Moreover, the importance of supportive school leadership emerges as critical. According to Channel, M. (2024), he used the theory of Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs that leaders should use this strategy to create a positive work environment and increase employee motivation. Teachers thrive in environments where administrators encourage participation in decision-making and provide emotional, moral, and professional support. Empowerment is not only a policy framework but a culture cultivated by school leaders. Lastly, the study affirms that teacher empowerment is not isolated from learner success. Theory of Self-efficacy by Bandura, A., possessed that teacher's belief in their ability to successfully perform specific teaching tasks and manage their classroom effectively. Empowered teachers translate their confidence and autonomy into improved instructional strategies, leading to more motivated, engaged, and successful learners. This supports the broader educational goal of quality and equitable learning outcomes across all contexts.

4.3. Future Directions—

Based on the study's findings, it is crucial that the results are effectively communicated and utilized by the key individuals for whom this research was designed.

Learners Future directions for learners focus on strengthening their active engagement in the learning process by promoting reciprocal agency between teachers and students. As the study has shown, empowered teachers are more likely to use inclusive and student-centered practices; therefore, schools should cultivate classroom environments where learners can express feedback, co-create learning activities, and build reflective habits. This participatory approach not only improves student motivation and academic achievement but also nurtures a sense of responsibility and autonomy among learners. Moving forward, integrating student voice into pedagogical design can foster mutual empowerment and collaborative growth in the classroom. **Teachers** Based on the findings, future directions for teachers should emphasize the need for sustained peer collaboration, professional reflection, and leadership opportunities within schools. Teachers are encouraged to engage in professional learning communities (PLCs), where they can exchange ideas, solve instructional challenges, and co-develop strategies aligned with learner needs. Additionally, advocating for teacher autonomy and pursuing leadership roles in curriculum design or policy implementation will enhance their sense of professional agency. Future teacher empowerment efforts must also prioritize well-being by supporting teachers in developing resilience practices, time management, and emotional self-care as part of their professional routines. **School Administrators** Future initiatives for school administrators should focus on institutionalizing teacher empowerment through inclusive leadership, participatory governance, and targeted support mechanisms. As shown in the study, administrators play a pivotal role in enabling or hindering teacher agency. Hence, school leaders

should establish feedback loops, conduct regular teacher-led consultations, and provide recognition programs that celebrate instructional innovation. Administrators must also ensure equitable access to teaching resources, time for collaboration, and capacity-building activities. **DepEd Officials** For the Department of Education (DepEd), future directions should involve the systemic embedding of empowerment principles in national education frameworks such as the PPST, SBM, and professional development plans. DepEd should initiate strategic programs that institutionalize school-based innovation funds, recognize teacher-led research, and address equity gaps across regions. In light of the study's findings, policies must be re-evaluated to ensure they promote flexibility, creativity, and teacher autonomy, particularly in the implementation of curricula and technology integration. Moreover, regional offices must closely monitor school empowerment practices and provide technical assistance to support local innovations in teaching and leadership. **Policymakers** Policymakers are urged to craft and enact legislation that protects and promotes teacher empowerment through structured policy reforms. This includes mandating reduced workload limits, establishing empowerment benchmarks in school accreditation, and allocating budget for continuous teacher development. Future policy directions should address systemic barriers—such as hierarchical decision-making, outdated evaluation systems, and inequitable funding—that restrict teacher agency. Emphasizing participatory policy development with teachers as co-authors of educational reform will ensure grounded and sustainable empowerment frameworks. **Future Researchers** Future researchers are encouraged to expand the scope of this study through longitudinal, comparative, and mixed-method investigations that deepen the understanding of teacher empowerment across diverse contexts. Longitudinal studies could trace the long-term impact of empowerment on teacher retention, learner

achievement, and school reform. Comparative analyses between urban and rural settings may uncover contextual disparities and innovations.

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